

How Artificial Intelligence is Going to Revolutionize the Non-Banking Financial Companies

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) will revolutionize the NBFCs with banking-like services sans a banking license. Similar to a bank, in nature and its activity, it faces different challenges related to risks, processes, customer service, and various other operational matters. AI stands as an innovative solution to these challenges, and therefore, the NBFCs are standing tall against this increasingly digital and data-driven world. This research aims to identify the domains of AI research in NBFCs. This study highlights the market's current scenarios and the need for AI technologies in NBFCs. Also, this study highlights the importance of AI in the NBFCs. AI provides new solutions to these challenges. Therefore, it offers tools that would assist NBFCs in operating efficiently and serving customers better, thus gradually declining the risks. NBFCs can streamline their process, alter the nature of customer interaction, and make decisions based on data through AI technologies, making them highly visionary financial sector players. This will further augment the growth and stability of NBFCs as they will be potent enough to thrive in a competitive market powered by AI's enhancements related to risk optimization, automation of operations, fraud detection, and personalized services.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Non-Banking Financial Companies; Operations; Financial Sector; Risks

1. Introduction

NBFCs played an essential role in meeting the financial needs of traditionally bank-un-served or under-served individuals and businesses (R. Kumar et al., 2023). However, regulations for NBFCs have been tightened recently, borrowing cost has gone up, and those NBFCs focus niche markets and personalized products and services (Yadav et al., 2022). Now, NBFCs focus more on innovative product development and low-income customers in urban markets of unorganized sectors. In this scenario, NBFC business and operation models powered by emerging technologies would provide seamless facilitation designs, launching, implementing and executing specially crafted products and services. New technologies, as well as strategic

partnerships with incumbent financial institutions and FinTechs, enable the NBFC also to reduce its costs of increasing its customer base, lowering the cost of acquiring customers, servicing existing customers, or de-risking the portfolio while trying to overcome the increasing formal credit penetration in a growing economy (Rahman et al., 2023).

The speed and extent of technological change are drastically transforming the financial services industry, especially in AI (Gonçalves et al., 2023). Non-banking financial companies, which have a critical position in the economic system by offering loans, investment solutions, and asset management, among others, are increasingly embracing AI to enhance their operative processes and delivery of services. AI can streamline operations and strengthen the decision-making processes of NBFCs, culminating in greater efficiency and customer satisfaction. AI will enable better customer engagement through chatbots and virtual assistants that offer personalized, anticipatory services for a better customer experience. Predictive analytics and machine learning models will help NBFCs to manage risk much better, detect fraud, and ensure compliance with all regulatory requirements, thus achieving greater operational efficiency and cost savings (Mhlanga, 2020; Zhu et al., 2024). For instance, intelligent automation can automate various kinds of financial activities like transactional activity, economic analysis, and fund management in the stock market with much less interference from the human factor and greater accuracy (Khuong Nguyen et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 2024). NBFCs for example, will be able to innovate faster than others by playing at a relatively even level against digital-native banks and credit unions in bringing customers closer to them with long-term growth and profitability ensured by leveraging AI, machine learning, and cloud computing.

AI is changing the face of the banking industry as it enhances the quality of products and services available (Arora et al., 2023). It simplifies and expedites traditional processes that take a long time while improving data management for an enhanced customer experience. In today's financial scenery, data is the most prized asset for banking institutions. They increasingly realize that AI and other technologies offer many new, innovative solutions at lower costs. Banks finally realize that success no longer depends on size but on their ability to wield technology to exploit their data (Cubric & Li, 2024). Adopting AI would alter the financial services industry in massive and integral ways. Customer relationship management, risk assessment, and even predictive analysis will take unprecedented heights with the participation of AI-based solutions. Banks will be better equipped to tailor services for

individual customers, improve operational efficiency, and help make better decisions through machine learning and natural language processing technologies.

2. Literature Review

(Branzoli et al., 2024) demonstrates a positive correlation between banks' extent of information technology (IT) implementation and the magnitude of corporate lending growth after the COVID-19 epidemic in Italy. The empirical evidence is that these outcomes are influenced by the bank's capacity to extend credit exclusively through online channels and its use of artificial intelligence for evaluating credit risk. The close physical distance between borrowers and lenders was crucial in facilitating credit provision during the epidemic, but only when accompanied by a significant degree of ICT implementation. Technology is well acknowledged as transforming the accounting profession, enabling accountants to concentrate on professional expertise and technical proficiencies that provide value for the organization's performance (Al-Okaily, 2024).

(Ashique Ali & Subramanian, 2024) The review consolidates prior Fintech literature on behavioural goals in banking by focusing on trust, security, and other aspects and identifying current research deficiencies. (Jackson & Allen, 2024) the factors of technology adoption, which included adopter characteristics, usability of the technology, industry characteristics, organizational leadership, and organizational features, all played a role in the process. It has been argued that the new model may be improved even further by including a new conceptualization known as leadership diversity, which had yet to be brought up in previous research.

(Aloulou et al., 2024) examined the positive stance of the United Arab Emirates (UAE) towards the digital transformation of the financial sector and the advancement of FinTech attributed to the emergence of financial technology. FinTech integrates pioneering ideas and advanced technology to offer financial inclusion to stakeholders via a range of novel goods and services, such as metaverse and artificial intelligence. The results suggest that implementing FinTech significantly influenced the competitiveness and performance of the banking sector in the UAE during the COVID-19 pandemic. Evidence suggests that the successful integration of FinTech and its synchronization with technology management directly impact the banking industry's performance in the UAE during challenging periods.

(Ngo & Nguyen, 2024) recommendations to promote the dual development of FinTech and the banking industry in Vietnam and other emerging economies with similar banking systems, this study seeks to identify the key factors driving consumer adoption attention towards FinTech services in a bank-based financial system. The study reveals that current bank customers are strongly inclined to engage with FinTech services, irrespective of the associated expenses and time commitments. This implies that the conventional banking system should facilitate collaboration with FinTech companies in potential business sectors. The results also demonstrate a strikingly significant role of consumers' latent wants in motivating them to use FinTech services in Vietnam. (Shbail et al., 2024) examines the pertinent narratives in annual reports and categorizes them into coherent themes, offering insights into the main areas of interest and connections.

(Awwad & El Khoury, 2024) evaluate the influence of IT governance on the financial performance of banks in Palestine while accounting for bank-specific and governance factors. The findings underscore the significance of IT governance and validate the necessity to enhance and refine the corporate governance regulations in Palestine to fortify IT governance. (Jafri et al., 2024) consolidates prior Fintech literature on behavioural goals in banking by focusing on trust, security, and other aspects and identifying current research deficiencies. A thematic analysis yields five main themes (UTAUT2 variables: risk, trust, quality, and others), further divided into 24 sub-themes. The weighted analysis highlights the most effective underutilized variables: performance expectancy, trust, security, perceived usefulness, and attitude. Furthermore, the study highlights areas lacking research and suggests future investigations utilizing the theoretical framework of the TCCM (Theory, Context, Constructs, and Method).

(Khattak et al., 2023) they examined how diversification affects institution stability throughout the digital transformation. The findings indicate that the allocation of resources towards technological advancements and the expansion of diversification heighten the vulnerability and fragility of banks. (Thakur et al., 2023) explored how ICT affects bank profitability. Policymakers, owners, and managers do not need to see ICT tools as crucial to a bank's long-term prosperity. The findings do not have any substantial impact on all parties involved, such as policymakers, shareholders, and management, in terms of considering the implementation of ICT tools as a crucial element in improving a bank's profitability in the long term.

3. Findings of the Study

3.1. *AI revolutionizing the NBFCs*

AI fundamentally changes the model of an NBFC, as it propels automation, personalisation, and risk management to unprecedented heights (Awwad & El Khoury, 2024). It allows for faster data-driven decision-making, cost reductions, and superior customer experience. With this revolution, NBFCs will be in a more formidable position to provide more inclusive financial services, manage risk better, and stay ahead in the increasingly technology-driven financial landscape (Young & Young, 2022). This revolution will make NBFCs more efficient, agile, and customer-centric, positioning them for the long haul. AI algorithms can now analyse financial and non-financial data to predict borrowers' creditworthiness and help NBFCs make faster, more accurate lending decisions. AI-based algorithms can help their customers by providing personalised financial products and services, which would automatically help NBFCs increase customer retention and satisfaction levels (Nazneen & Dhawan, 2018). Analysis of customer feedback and sentiment can help the NBFC understand customer satisfaction and where improvements are necessary. With AI-based OCR, verification of documents can be done speedily and accurately, thus reducing human intervention and time needed for processing documents. AI-powered robo-advisors can help NBFCs manage client investment portfolios by providing insights, making data-driven investment decisions, and optimizing asset allocation (Dutta et al., 2020). AI-driven systems will automate reminders and personalized communication with borrowers to make collections smoother. AI can free many simple, low-value jobs - such as data entry, reporting, and auditing - to let people be strategic (Basu & Bawa, 2022).

3.2. *Risks associated with AI in NBFCs*

While AI significantly benefits Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs), it also presents several risks and challenges. These risks can stem from technology limitations, regulatory concerns, data management issues, and operational vulnerabilities. AI systems require vast amounts of data, including personal and financial information (Kannan et al., 2019). Poorly implemented security protocols can expose sensitive customer data to unauthorized access, hacking, or breaches (Sharma et al., 2021). AI systems can perpetuate or introduce biases in decision-making, primarily as they rely on biased datasets. This leads to unfair lending practices. Certain customer groups are wrongfully denied loans or charged higher interest rates because of their demographic characteristics, such as race, gender, or socioeconomic

status. Blind reliance on AI-generated outputs without human oversight leads to a blurred line between decisions and, more crucially, flawed decisions made when models are built on incorrect or incomplete assumptions (Taghizadeh-Hesary & Yoshino, 2020). Over-reliance on such AI models to process loan applications, credit scoring, or risk assessment can lead to financial losses simply because these models fail to capture specific dynamics in the market. The regulatory framework for AI use in financial services remains in its infancy. An NBFC may face compliance difficulties because of the lack of clear guidelines on how AI-driven processes should adhere to the existing financial regulations (Buch & Goldberg, 2022).

3.3. AI-based chatbots as an advisers

From providing basic customer service, AI-based chatbots have moved ahead into financial advisory roles in NBFCs. Indeed, AI-based systems can allow customers to seek various financial services with tailored advice and recommendations (Thakor, 2020). AI-powered chatbots will give user-specific advice based on his financial history, expenditure habits, income, and goal aim. For instance, they can suggest appropriate loan items, saving plans, or investment options based on the user profile. They can provide real-time financial advice, answering loan-related queries, investment queries, and credit scores or debt management inquiries immediately. They can also alert the customer of significant financial dates, such as loan repayment due dates or payment schedules, to keep them on track (Chen et al., 2021). The AI-based chatbots can assist customers in determining loan eligibility based on their credit history, income, and other relevant financial data. This way, they can be able to guide the customers on the availed loan products and provide them with real-time pre-approvals based on such an analysis. Integrated AI-based robo-advisors can help customers with investment advice through market trends, economic data, and customer goals. They can hence suggest the appropriate investment portfolios given the risk tolerance, investment horizon, and financial objectives (Nizam et al., 2019). When the customer is laden with debt, AI chatbots can suggest customized payment plans. It can also notify customers when they are at risk of missing a payment or suggest how to avoid late fees or penalties. AI-powered chatbots help reduce costs for NBFCs as many advisory functions that would otherwise require manpower can be automated by the implementation of AI-powered chatbots (Bhatia et al., 2020). The financial services, in general, become accessible and more affordable to a wider market clientele.

3.4. Enhancing Customer Experience

Beyond efficiency, these AI-based systems greatly improve the customer experience. Digital tools can carry out smooth, user-friendly applications to obtain a loan, upload documents, and check on loan status at any time, from anywhere. Such comfort attracts those high-tech consumers who prefer online transaction more than traditional, paper-based transactions (Khattak et al., 2023). Beyond that, AI-based customer service solutions with chatbots and automated advisors engage in timely support and consultancy to further amplify the satisfaction level for customers. AI can take customer data regarding demographics, spending habits, and financial objectives, among others, to deliver highly personalized financial solutions. For example, these may involve suggesting loan products, investment options, or other savings plans according to individual customer needs (R. Kumar et al., 2023). AI tools monitor customer behavior and send timely alerts or updates, like due date reminders for loan payments, possible credit score enhancement tips, or fraud detection messages. Loan applications can be simplified by eliminating paperwork and instantly verifying documents through AI and automation, leading to faster approvals and a seamless customer journey. AI-driven loyalty programs rewarding customers for prompt loan repayment, referrals, or product usage can help engender long-term relationships (Khanna & Haldar, 2022). The program's effectiveness would be significantly enhanced by personalizing the rewards based on customer behavior. AI tools can analyze customer feedback from multiple sources (social media, emails, surveys) to gauge real-time customer sentiment. This helps NBFCs identify pain points and take timely actions to improve services.

3.5. Market Forecasting in NBFCs using AI

AI and machine learning transform market forecasting in NBFCs by rendering predictions and resultant decision-making significantly more accurate (Darapaneni et al., 2022). Leverage AI-driven forecasting models to achieve better risk management, optimize lending and investment strategies, and be responsive to changing market conditions. However, successful implementation requires these various qualifications: data quality, model transparency, and balanced integration of human expertise and AI. AI and ML have transformed market forecasting by significantly increasing accuracy and speed because they can handle vast datasets and identify complex patterns, improving predictive power. AI models can analyze unstructured data from news articles, social media, and financial reports to gauge market sentiment (Matsepe & Van der Lingen, 2022). This helps predict market trends by knowing public and investor sentiment. AI models can predict future loan demand

by checking lending history data, economic conditions, market trends, and customer behavior. An accurate loan demand forecast helps the NBFCs well manage their liquidity and resources. Forecasting helps the NBFCs prepare for loan demand due to changes in interest rate shifts, regulatory reforms, or macroeconomic events. AI-based forecasting models can predict potential scenarios of defaultable loans based on credit data developed from information related to customer loans, historical financial information, and overall trends in the economy (Wu et al., 2022). This allows the effective strengthening of credit risk management and fine-tuning of lending activities with predictions. AI-based models can also predict instances of an economic downturn and other risks that would make borrowers not pay back their loans. Precise prediction of interest rates means NBFCs may come up with suitable interest rates and profitability structures. It can also study macroeconomic indicators like inflation and monetary policies of central banks to predict interest rate policy changes, which might help the NBFC in adjusting loan pricing strategies accordingly. AI can analyze social media, financial news, and online forums to gauge the market sentiment and investor behavior, which can be factors in investment strategies or loan product offerings. For instance, if the sentiment in the housing industry takes a negative turn, the NBFC can anticipate that there will be lesser demand for house loans (Hussain et al., 2019). AI-based models of economics predict macroeconomic variables, such as GDP, inflation, and unemployment rates. It alerts the NBFC about the larger economic trends in the loans, credit risk, and profitability (Parayil Iqbal et al., 2022).

3.6. Faster Loan Processing and Reduced Costs

Most importantly, AI is automating operations in NBFCs. Loan processing approval days are no longer manual with tiring lines of paper work. This is the sea change loan processing has witnessed due to AI (Agyapong, 2020). For example, risk profile of a borrower can be profiled through credit scores, the financial history, or even through social media activity through AI-based underwriting tools. This would enable the NBFCs to process loan applications significantly faster with enhanced accuracy, thus making it possible for customers to get approved faster and to get access to funds faster (Baral et al., 2023). It forms an important goal for the NBFCs in these times of hot competition and rising expectations from customers. The introduction of artificial intelligence and automation is changing the way NBFCs handle loan applications, approvals, disbursements, and risk assessment, including both the speed of the process and lower operational costs (A. Kumar et al., 2021; Zhao & Khaliq, 2024). Mobile apps or web-based facilities enable customers to apply for

loans and automatically collect initial data without manual paperwork while speeding up the process (Nagariya et al., 2023). Traditional credit scoring often takes time and does not consider non-traditional data. AI algorithms can analyse a broader set of data, including transactional history, social media behavior, and alternative credit scoring metrics, to instantly assess a customer's creditworthiness (Al-Debei et al., 2024; Bian et al., 2024; Maniam, 2024). AI can determine the risk level associated with each loan application and offer risk-based pricing to enable NBFCs to offer loan terms and interest that could be customised (Mukherjee & Chittipaka, 2022). The loans are managed better by reducing exposure to probable default cases (Singh et al., 2021). AI can enable instant loan approval or loan rejection based on predefined rules, which helps greatly in speeding up the process of decision-making (Roy, Ravindra, et al., 2023). High risks will be flagged for manual approvals and the lower risks are instant. Such loan processing AI systems may flag suspicious transactions or discrepancies in the data of the customer when loan issuance is in process for efficient compliance with anti-money laundering regulations (Jaiswal et al., 2023). Once the loan is approved, the AI system can instantly give an instant disbursement, minus human intervention, of funds through digital payment channels such as bank transfer and mobile wallets. This reduces the time-to-disbursement and enhances customer experience (Baliker et al., 2024; Puschmann & Khmarskyi, 2024; Rizvi et al., 2024). The data analytics through AI-driven would help NBFCs predict customer behavior, identify potential defaults early on, then change loan terms, Koloseni & Mandari (2024) and S. ur Rahman et al., 2024 and Riahi & Garrouch, 2024. That proactive approach will mitigate risks and manage the loan portfolio in a manner which reduces bad loans' costs (Roy, Babakerkhell, et al., 2022).

4. Discussion

AI will revolutionize NBFCs at several key levels—efficiency, customer-centricity, and competitiveness (Roy, Babakerkhell, et al., 2023; Roy, Chekuri, et al., 2023). It will use creditworthiness assessment with absolute precision by scanning millions of pieces of data on customers' behavior, transaction history, and social activity through AI algorithms (Baabdullah et al., 2019). With AI, an NBFC can reduce its bad loans, identify the potential defaulters ahead in time, and extend loans to those classes that were always unbanked by analyzing alternative credit data sources (Mukherjee, Baral, Pal, et al., 2022; Roy, Baral, et al., 2022). This will enable NBFCs to extend custom credit products along with appropriate terms pertaining to the particular customer's actual risk. AI can identify anomalies in the patterns of transaction that otherwise cannot be detected (Mukherjee, Baral, & Chittipaka,

2022; Mukherjee, Baral, Chittipaka, et al., 2022). NBFCs can detect suspicious transactions and block losses immediately with the use of ML techniques (M. Rahman et al., 2022). AI models learn about fraud cases and determine predictions that will be highly accurate in the future (Mariemuthu, 2019). AI enables NBFCs to offer tailored products and services to customers.

Using such chatbots, virtual assistants, and AI-driven CRM systems, NBFCs would boost engagement among customers by accessing help 24/7, faster resolution of queries, and more personalized financial advice (Breidbach et al., 2020). AI can also analyze customer preferences to suggest investment options or loan products that would meet individual needs. AI-driven automation can also streamline back-office operations, underwriting, document verification, and compliance checks (Lee & Chen, 2022). This reduces the element of human error, decreases costs, and accelerates the processes related to loan sanctioning, thereby increasing the level of customer satisfaction (Shbail et al., 2024). RPA can automate repetitive business functions, thus freeing time for humans to engage in other more strategic missions. AI solutions can more aptly enable NBFCs in adhering to the compliance requirements with the aid of automation of numerous compliance checks, reports, and data (Fosso Wamba et al., 2020). AI will track all the changes in regulations and allow the company's activities to be compliant with the laws always, reducing the risk of penalties or lawsuits (Du et al., 2019). It can predict market trends, customer behavior, and operational risks so NBFCs can make decisions backed up by data.

Predictive analytics contributes to the creation of new business opportunities, liquidity management, and forecasting financial performance (Chaklader et al., 2023). This paves the way for long-term growth and stability of NBFCs. AI maximizes loan recovery through the identification of the best strategy for collecting defaulting amounts (Tran et al., 2024). Based on the scrutiny of borrower profiles, AI develops a bespoke strategy for repaying loans, thereby improving recovery rates with little loss of relationships (Milian et al., 2019). In other words, infusion of AI in NBFCs is not a fad; it is a must to survive in a highly competitive financial environment (Belanche et al., 2019). With its ability to enhance risk management, become more efficient in operations, and improve customer satisfaction, AI can help drive the sector to enormous growth and innovation (Liu et al., 2024). With AI, NBFCs can be operational streamliners and open up markets and customer groups for themselves (Tello-Gamarra et al., 2022). AI implementation by NBFCs affords it efficiency, reduced costs, and customer satisfaction (Harris & Wonglimpiyarat, 2023; Sandhu et al., 2023). AI enables

NBFCs to prosper under such a fast-changing financial environment as it would lead to better decision-making, risks, and personalization (Issa et al., 2023). AI ultimately drives the long-term growth of NBFCs through innovative and inclusive customer-centered services (Kowalewski & Pisany, 2023).

5. Conclusion

With AI poised to revolutionise the operations of NBFCs, efficiency in operational activities pertaining to servicing customers and managing risks is improved. Through the roots of automation, personalized services, fraud detection, and data-driven insights, AI aids in faster and more accurate financial solutions delivery by NBFCs at the same time reducing costs and errors. That aside, AI increases the access reach of NBFCs and delivers financial services to otherwise underserved markets, a new dimension towards financial inclusion. The AI embracing NBFCs will be in place to innovate, maintain competitiveness, and drive sustainable growth as the financial services landscape continues to evolve.

References

- Al-Okaily, M. (2024). Attitudes toward the adoption of accounting analytics technology in the digital transformation landscape. *Journal of Accounting and Organizational Change, ahead-of-print*(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAOC-04-2024-0127/FULL/PDF>
- Aloulou, M., Grati, R., Al-Qudah, A. A., & Al-Okaily, M. (2024). Does FinTech adoption increase the diffusion rate of digital financial inclusion? A study of the banking industry sector. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting, 22*(2), 289–307. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-05-2023-0224/FULL/PDF>
- Arora, A., Gupta, S., Devi, C., & Walia, N. (2023). Customer experiences in the era of artificial intelligence (AI) in context to FinTech: a fuzzy AHP approach. *Benchmarking, 30*(10), 4342–4369. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-10-2021-0621/FULL/PDF>
- Ashique Ali, K. A., & Subramanian, R. (2024). Current Status of Research on Mobile Banking: An Analysis of Literature. *Vision, 28*(1), 7–18. https://doi.org/10.1177/09722629211073268/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_09722629211073268-FIG8.JPEG
- Awwad, B., & El Khoury, R. (2024). Information technology governance and bank performance: evidence from Palestine. *Journal of Decision Systems, 33*(2), 311–334. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12460125.2021.2005860>
- Baral, M. M., Rao, U. V. A., Rao, K. S., Dey, G. C., Mukherjee, S., & Kumar, M. A. (2023). Achieving Sustainability of SMEs Through Industry 4.0-Based Circular Economy. *International Journal of Global Business and Competitiveness*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42943-023-00074-2>
- Basu, S., & Bawa, J. (2022). *Shadow Banking and Non-banking Financial Companies in India: An Overview* (pp. 187–204). Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-7668-0_10
- Branzoli, N., Rainone, E., & Supino, I. (2024). The role of banks' technology adoption in credit markets during the pandemic. *Journal of Financial Stability, 71*, 101230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFS.2024.101230>

- Buch, C. M., & Goldberg, L. S. (2022). Complexity and riskiness of banking organizations: Evidence from the International Banking Research Network. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 134, 106244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JBANKFIN.2021.106244>
- Chen, Y., Kumara, E. K., & Sivakumar, V. (2021). Investigation of finance industry on risk awareness model and digital economic growth. *Annals of Operations Research*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10479-021-04287-7/TABLES/3>
- Cubric, M., & Li, F. (2024). Bridging the ‘Concept–Product’ gap in new product development: Emerging insights from the application of artificial intelligence in FinTech SMEs. *Technovation*, 134, 103017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TECHNOVATION.2024.103017>
- Darapaneni, N., Kumar, A., Dixit, A., Suriyanarayanan, M., Srivastava, S., & Paduri, A. R. (2022). Loan Prediction Software for Financial Institutions. *2022 International Conference on Interdisciplinary Research in Technology and Management, IRTM 2022 - Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IRTM54583.2022.9791797>
- Dutta, P., Jain, A., & Gupta, A. (2020). Performance analysis of non-banking finance companies using two-stage data envelopment analysis. *Annals of Operations Research*, 295(1), 91–116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10479-020-03705-6/FIGURES/4>
- Gonçalves, A. R., Breda Meira, A., Shuqair, S., & Costa Pinto, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence (AI) in FinTech decisions: the role of congruity and rejection sensitivity. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 41(6), 1282–1307. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-07-2022-0295/FULL/PDF>
- Jackson, D., & Allen, C. (2024). Technology adoption in accounting: the role of staff perceptions and organisational context. *Journal of Accounting and Organizational Change*, 20(2), 205–227. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAOC-01-2023-0007/FULL/PDF>
- Jafri, J. A., Mohd Amin, S. I., Abdul Rahman, A., & Mohd Nor, S. (2024). A systematic literature review of the role of trust and security on Fintech adoption in banking. *Heliyon*, 10(1), 22980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.HELIYON.2023.E22980/ASSET/A3138DAD-B907-43B9-9798-A6A68417414A/MAIN.ASSETS/GR4.JPG>
- Kannan, R., Shanmugam, K. R., & Bhaduri, S. (2019). *Non-Banking Financial Companies Role in India's Development*. Springer Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-3375-0>
- Khanna, P., & Haldar, A. (2022). Will adoption of blockchain technology be challenging: evidence from Indian banking industry. *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets*, 15(2), 361–384. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QRFM-01-2022-0003/FULL/PDF>
- Khattak, M. A., Ali, M., Azmi, W., & Rizvi, S. A. R. (2023). Digital transformation, diversification and stability: What do we know about banks? *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 78, 122–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EAP.2023.03.004>
- Matsepe, N. T., & Van der Lingen, E. (2022). Determinants of emerging technologies adoption in the South African financial sector. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 53(1). <https://doi.org/10.4102/SAJBM.V53I1.2493>
- Mhlanga, D. (2020). Industry 4.0 in Finance: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Digital Financial Inclusion. *International Journal of Financial Studies 2020, Vol. 8, Page 45*, 8(3), 45. <https://doi.org/10.3390/IJFS8030045>
- Mukherjee, S., Baral, M. M., & Chittipaka, V. (2022). Studying the Adoption of Blockchain Technology in the Manufacturing Firms. In *Utilizing Blockchain Technologies in Manufacturing and Logistics Management* (pp. 64–80). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8697-6.ch004>

- Mukherjee, S., Baral, M. M., Chittipaka, V., & Pal, S. K. (2022). A Structural Equation Modelling Approach to Develop a Resilient Supply Chain Strategy for the COVID-19 Disruptions. In *Handbook of Research on Supply Chain Resiliency, Efficiency, and Visibility in the Post-Pandemic Era* (pp. 242–266). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-9506-0.ch013>
- Mukherjee, S., Baral, M. M., Pal, S. K., Chittipaka, V., Roy, R., & Alam, K. (2022). Humanoid robot in healthcare: A Systematic Review and Future Research Directions. *2022 International Conference on Machine Learning, Big Data, Cloud and Parallel Computing (COM-IT-CON)*, 822–826. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COM-IT-CON54601.2022.9850577>
- Mukherjee, S., & Chittipaka, V. (2022). Analysing the Adoption of Intelligent Agent Technology in Food Supply Chain Management: An Empirical Evidence. *FIIB Business Review*, 11(4), 438–454. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23197145211059243>
- Nagariya, R., Mukherjee, S., Baral, M. M., & Chittipaka, V. (2023). Analyzing blockchain-based supply chain resilience strategies: resource-based perspective. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-07-2022-0330>
- Nazneen, A., & Dhawan, S. (2018). A Review of Role and Challenges of Non-Banking Financial Companies in Economic Development of India *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues* A Review of Role and Challenges of Non-banking Financial Companies in Economic Development of India. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 8(6), 90–98. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijefi.7220>
- Ngo, H. T., & Nguyen, L. T. H. (2024). Consumer adoption intention toward FinTech services in a bank-based financial system in Vietnam. *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*, 32(2), 153–167. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRC-08-2021-0061/FULL/PDF>
- Parayil Iqbal, U., Jose, S. M., & Tahir, M. (2022). Integrating trust with extended UTAUT model: a study on Islamic banking customers' m-banking adoption in the Maldives. *Journal of Islamic Marketing, ahead-of-print*(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-01-2022-0030/FULL/PDF>
- Rahman, M., Ming, T. H., Baigh, T. A., & Sarker, M. (2023). Adoption of artificial intelligence in banking services: an empirical analysis. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 18(10), 4270–4300. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-06-2020-0724/FULL/PDF>
- Roy, R., Babakerkhell, M. D., Mukherjee, S., Pal, D., & Funilkul, S. (2022). Evaluating the Intention for the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence-Based Robots in the University to Educate the Students. *IEEE Access*, 10, 125666–125678. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3225555>
- Roy, R., Babakerkhell, M. D., Mukherjee, S., Pal, D., & Funilkul, S. (2023). Development of a framework for metaverse in education: A systematic literature review approach. *IEEE Access*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3283273>
- Roy, R., Baral, M. M., Pal, S. K., Kumar, S., Mukherjee, S., & Jana, B. (2022). Discussing the present, past, and future of Machine learning techniques in livestock farming: A systematic literature review. *2022 International Conference on Machine Learning, Big Data, Cloud and Parallel Computing (COM-IT-CON)*, 179–183. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COM-IT-CON54601.2022.9850749>
- Roy, R., Chekuri, K., Prasad, J. L., & Mukherjee, S. (2023). Discussing the Future Perspective of Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence in COVID-19 Vaccination: A Review. In *Applications of Computational Intelligence in Management & Mathematics* (pp. 151–160). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-25194-8_12
- Roy, R., Ravindra, M., Marada, N., Mukherjee, S., & Baral, M. M. (2023). Machine Learning Techniques for the Prediction of Bovine Tuberculosis Among the Cattle. In *Proceedings of International Conference on*

- Data Science and Applications* (Volume no-551, Vol. 1, pp. 295–303). Proceedings of International Conference on Data Science and Applications. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 551. Springer, Singapore. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-6631-6_21
- Sharma, A., Rastogi, S., & Elmagrhi, M. H. (2021). Impact of Efficiency on Voluntary Disclosure of Non-Banking Financial Company—Microfinance Institutions in India. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management 2021, Vol. 14, Page 289, 14(7)*, 289. <https://doi.org/10.3390/JRFM14070289>
- Shbail, M. O. Al, Jaradat, Z., Baker, M. B., & Almuet, M. (2024). Individual and technological factors affecting the adoption of enterprise resource planning systems in the Jordanian banking sector. *International Journal of Business Information Systems, 45(1)*, 118–141. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBIS.2024.135972>
- Taghizadeh-Hesary, F., & Yoshino, N. (2020). Sustainable Solutions for Green Financing and Investment in Renewable Energy Projects. *Energies 2020, Vol. 13, Page 788, 13(4)*, 788. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN13040788>
- Thakor, A. V. (2020). Fintech and banking: What do we know? *Journal of Financial Intermediation, 41*, 100833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFI.2019.100833>
- Thakur, S., Rastogi, S., Parashar, N., Tejasmayee, P., & Kappal, J. M. (2023). The Impact of ICT on the Profitability of Indian Banks: The Moderating Role of NPA. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management 2023, Vol. 16, Page 211, 16(4)*, 211. <https://doi.org/10.3390/JRFM16040211>
- Wang, C.-K., Masukujjaman, M., Syed, S., Alam, I., Ahmad, C.-Y., Lin, Y.-H., Ho, 2023, Shah Alam, S., Ahmad, I., Lin, C.-Y., & Ho, Y.-H. (2023). The Effects of Service Quality Performance on Customer Satisfaction for Non-Banking Financial Institutions in an Emerging Economy. *International Journal of Financial Studies 2023, Vol. 11, Page 33, 11(1)*, 33. <https://doi.org/10.3390/IJFS11010033>
- Yadav, H., Kar, A. K., & Kashiramka, S. (2022). Artificial Intelligence Adoption for FinTech Industries - An Exploratory Study About the Disruptions, Antecedents and Consequences. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics), 13454 LNCS*, 3–12. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-15342-6_1/COVER
- Young, D., & Young, J. (2022). Technology adoption: impact of FinTech on financial inclusion of low-income households. *International Journal of Electronic Finance, 11(3)*, 202–218. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEF.2022.124480>
- Zhu, H., Vigren, O., & Söderberg, I. L. (2024). Implementing artificial intelligence empowered financial advisory services: A literature review and critical research agenda. *Journal of Business Research, 174*, 114494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JBUSRES.2023.114494>